

Terpenoids. Part CVIII: Synthesis of dl-epi-Bicyclosesquiphellandrene

O. P. VIG, V. D. AHUJA, V. K. SEHGAL and S. D. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh.

Manuscript received 30 May 1975; accepted 5 April 1976.

α -formylated menthone (IV) on treatment with methyl vinyl ketone in the presence of triethylamine gives diketoaldehyde (V). Deformylation of (V) followed by cyclisation of the resulting diketone (VI) under basic conditions produces α, β -unsaturated ketone VII. Wittig reaction with methylene triphenyl phosphorane on (VII) furnishes epi-bicyclosesquiphellandrene (I).

BOTH bicyclosesquiphellandrene and 1-epibicyclosesquiphellandrene have been recently shown¹ to occur in the essential oils of *Piper cubeba* L and *Ocimum basilicum* L. respectively. These epimeric compounds have been assigned the constitutions 1- β (H), 7 α (H), 10 β (H)-cadina-4(14), 5-diene(II) and 1 α (H), 7 α (H), 10 β (H) cadina 4(14), -5-diene (I) depending upon their chemical behaviour and spectral data.

In continuation of our work on the synthesis of terpenoids through Wittig olefinations^{2,3}, we report here an elegant synthesis of the title bicyclic hydrocarbon (I) through a sequence of reaction depicted in chart I.

Racemic menthone (III) secured by the oxidation of menthol was formylated with ethyl formate in the presence of Na/C₂H₅OH in anhydrous benzene to produce IV in high yield. Treatment of IV with methyl vinyl ketone in triethylamine⁴ furnished diketoaldehyde (V), which was subsequently deformylated with 2% ethanolic K₂CO₃ to provide diketone(VI) in 70% yield.

Cyclisation of the diketone VI with KOH⁵ yielded unsaturated ketone (VII) whose semi carbazide derivative had a melting point of 139°-140° (lit⁶, m.p. 140°).

Finally, ketone (VII) was submitted to Wittig reaction with methylenetriphenylphosphorane to produce epi-bicyclosesquiphellandrene(I). The identity of the synthesised compound was substantiated by comparing its IR, UV and NMR with that reported in lit.¹.

Experimental

M.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. IR Spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer using thin liquid films. NMR spectrum was recorded using CCl₄ as solvent and TMS as internal standard at 60 MHz.

2-Formyl-2-methyl-6-isopropylcyclohexanone (IV)

To the anion, prepared from finally divided, Na (6.3 g) and ketone (III, 37 g) using benzene as solvent containing a small amount of absolute alcohol, was added ethyl formate (20.5 g) with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for 3 hr and left overnight. After usual work up and distillation under reduced pressure gave α -formylketone (IV, 30 g) in 81% yield. (Found: C, 72.43; H, 9.86. C₁₁H₁₈O₂ requires C, 72.49; H, 9.96%).

2-Formyl-2-(3-oxobutyl)-3-methyl-6-isopropylcyclohexanone (V)

To a mixture of ketoaldehyde (IV, 15 g) and MVK (12 g) was added 8.4 g of triethylamine with stirring and cooling. The reaction mixture was then cooled in ice bath for 1 hr. and allowed to stand for 3 days at room temp. After working up and subsequent distillation provided diketo-aldehyde (V, 10.5 g) in 70% yield, b.p. 185°-190°/7 mm; γ_{max} 2710, 1710-1690 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 71.42; H, 9.54. C₁₅H₂₄O₃ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.59%).

2 α (H)-2-(3-Oxobutyl)-3-methyl-6-isopropylcyclohexanone (VI)

The solution of 1 g of K_2CO_3 in 6 ml. of water was added to a solution of 15 g diketoaldehyde in 35 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 hrs. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether. Evaporation of the solvent followed by distillation under reduced pressure afforded diketone (VI, 11 g) in 70% yield, b.p. $168^\circ-75^\circ/6$ mm, γ_{max} 1710 cm^{-1} ($-C=O$). (Found: C, 74.81; H, 10.83. $C_{14}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 74.95; H, 10.78%).

10 α (H)-5-methyl-8-isopropyl-9-en-2-decalone (VII)

The solution of 9.2 g KOH in 77 ml of water was added dropwise to refluxing mixture of diketone (VI, 8.39 g) and KOH (0.8 g) in 192 ml of water. Refluxing was continued for 8 hrs. and cooled. After extracting the aqueous layer with ether and removal of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation under diminished pressure produced the α, β -unsaturated ketone (VII, 4.8 g) in 58% yield, b.p. $145^\circ-52^\circ/4$ mm; γ_{max} 1695 cm^{-1} (Found: C, 81.46; H, 10.08. $C_{14}H_{22}O$ requires C, 81.50; H, 10.15%). Semicarbazone, m.p. $139^\circ-40^\circ$ (from aq. ethanol), lit⁵ m.p. 140° . (Found: N, 15.87. $C_{15}H_{25}ON_3$ requires N, 15.96%).

1 α (H), 7 α (H), 10 β (H)-Cadina-4(14), 5-diene(I)

The phosphorane was prepared from NaH (0.432 g), DMSO (4.3 ml.) and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (3.7 g) in DMSO (8.6 ml) under nitrogen. To

this was added ketone (VII, 1.2 g) in THF (3 ml) and stirring was continued for 2 hr. Usual work up, followed by removal of the solvent gave the crude product. This was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina and subsequent distillation to afford epibicycloses quiphellandrene (1.09 g) in 75% yield, m.p. $145^\circ-50^\circ/8$ mm; γ_{max} $3115, 1640, 1600, 1450, 1380, 1195, 1110, 915$ and 890 cm^{-1} . 60 MHz NMR Spectrum showed signals at $\tau(CCl_4)$: 9.24 (3H, d, $-3CH_3$), 9.03 (6H, d, isopropylmethyl), 5.45 (2H, methylene protons) and 4.02 (1H, olefinic proton). $\lambda_{max}^{ethanol} = 239\text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon 10800$). These values are consistent with those reported in lit¹ for epibicyclosesquiphellandrene (I). (Found: C, 88.31; H, 11.70. $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. Sujan Singh (B.H.U.) for recording the NMR spectrum.

References

1. S. J. TERHUNE, J. W. HOGG and B. M. LAWRENCE, *Phytochemistry*, 1974, 13, 1183.
2. O. P. VIG, J. P. SALOTA and BALDEV VIG, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 323.
3. O. P. VIG, K. L. MATTA, GURDEEP SINGH and INDER RAJ., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 42, 581.
4. E. J. COREY and S. NOZOE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 5728.
5. J. COLONGE, J. DREUX and J. P. KEHLSTADT., *Bull. Soc. Chem. Fr.*, 1954, 1404.
6. P. H. LADWA, G. D. JOSHI and S. N. KULKARNI, *Chem. Ind.*, 1968, 1601.